

Status of Quality of Education and Distribution of Educational Facilities in Meja Block of Prayagraj District

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Abstract

Rural areas frequently face challenges like poverty, insufficient access to good education, inadequate healthcare services, and restricted employment options. Meja, similar to numerous other rural regions, suffers from inequalities affecting rural areas, evident in the limited availability of quality education. This paper seeks to assess the level of education services in the villages of Meja block. To do an analysis of the facilities, questionnaire was used which sought to collect data related to various variables of education. The responses were then processed using simple statistical techniques to devise a "Education Facilities Index". People were also asked the main issues that they face in accessing education facilities. Government schemes of both central and state governments related to providing and facilitating education are also enumerated.

Keywords

Inequalities, education facilities, government schemes, rural development.

Introduction

Rural communities often suffer with issues such as poverty, lack of access to quality education, inadequate healthcare facilities and limited employment opportunities. Meja, like many rural areas, grapples with the ongoing struggle to align with the broader trajectory of progress. Meja block remains an example of the persistent disparities that plague rural areas, manifesting in the form of limited access to quality education services. These issues and challenges not only negatively impact individuals' living conditions but also create obstacles in the course of their overall progress. (Kapur, 2019).

Objective of study

1. To assess the quality of education services available in the villages of Meja block.
2. To understand the perception of issues and challenges faced by residents of the study area in accessing education services in villages of Meja block.
3. To enumerate the steps taken by national and state governments regarding education.

Review of Literature

Education is a crucial component of human resource development, playing a vital role in enhancing the well-being of individuals by elevating income levels and standards of living. (Nishad, P., Sinha, B.R.K., 2021). It is an established fact that in the world only those nations have made progress and development which have a sound education system. (Barick, K, 2016) Access to quality education serves as a catalyst for improved health outcomes in several ways. A literate population is more likely to comprehend and adhere to healthcare guidelines, contributing to the prevention and early detection of illnesses. This paper endeavours to unravel the multifaceted issues confronting the educational sector in the villages of Meja block, shedding light on the barriers that impede progress and wellbeing.

Study area:

Meja block is one of the 20 blocks in Prayagraj district, Uttar Pradesh, India. The total area of Meja is 436.63 sq. km and total population is 1,97,086. The male population is 1,02,828 while the female count is 94,258. This population comprises of 31,244 households. The block consists of 159 villages out of which 150 are inhabited villages and 9 are uninhabited.

Methodology

A detailed questionnaire was prepared which had questions related to various variables of education facilities available in the study area. In the methodology employed, participants were queried on the availability, quality, and accessibility of educational services within their respective villages. Employing a random sampling methodology, six responses were garnered from individuals within each of the 150 inhabited villages, resulting in a total of 900 respondents across the study area. Each participant's responses were systematically coded, with a numerical scale ranging from 1, indicating the optimal scenario to 5, signifying the least desirable situation. This coding system allowed for the quantification of subjective responses, enabling a structured analysis of the data. Using simple statistical methods, individual responses within each village were then consolidated, generating a single value for each village in relation to

each aspect under investigation. The cumulative responses for were integrated to compute an overall code- "Educational facilities index", providing a holistic assessment of each village's standing across multiple parameters of education. This cumulative score, was further utilized to classify the villages into distinct categories, enabling a comprehensive interpretation of the data and the identification of the patterns of education facilities within the study area. For better representation purposes, a choropleth map using ArcGIS version 10.3 is also given.

Description of variables:

Q1 denotes the first variable as to how satisfied the respondents were with the quality of education provided in their village, Q2 is the second variable denotes the distance the children have to travel to access educational facilities. The options given in each question related to all the variables and the respective code assigned for each of the response are given in the following table.

Table 1: Response options and their corresponding codes for Education facilities.

S. No.	Q1 Responses	Q1 Code	Q2 Responses	Q2 Code
1	Very satisfied	1	Less than 1 kilometre	1
2	Satisfied	2	1-2 kilometers	2
3	Neutral	3	2-5 kilometers	3
4	Dissatisfied	4	5-10 kilometers	4
5	Very dissatisfied	5	> 10 kilometers	5

Source: Methodology adopted by researcher.

Result and Discussion

The village wise response on each parameter is cumulated. Based on this cumulative score, where lower score represents better case scenario and higher the score, the worse is the condition of the selected education parameters. Largest number of the villages- total of 72 falls in the neutral category of the educational facilities index. The next largest number- around a quarter of the total fall in "low" category of the educational facilities index. A very low number of villages only 4 of 150 inhabited villages in the block are in the highest category of the index.

Table 2: Categories of villages based on Total score

S. No.	Class Intervals	Names of villages.	Number of Villages	% of villages
1	19-23.6	Gopalpur, Kauhat, Kohrar, Kurki Kalan	4	2.67
2	23.6-28.2	Amkachha, Atari Amiliya, Baddiha, Bhaiya, Bhatauti, Bhoj purva, Bisahijan kala, Chandra Udaya, Dighalo, Etawa Khurd, Gat, Ghoraha, Gunai Gaharpur, Hardihan, Karah, Khara, Khoota, Kulbhasa, Mai Khurd, Marar, Meja Khas, Mojara, Nartir, Pausiya Dube, Salaiya Kala, Silaudhi Khurd, Udhrenga	27	18%
3	28.2-32.8	Akhari Shahpur, Amora, Badhava, Bairghat, Belahan, Bhabhaur, Bhasundar Khurd, Bhasunder Mijhali, Busaka, Chamariapur, Chandhash, Chandkhamarihia, Chapartala Tappa, Chaurasi, Chapro, Derhan, Dhadhuva, Dharaval, Dhauhan, Chehra, Dihi khurd, Gadurahi, Gaharpur Khurd, Gaura, Ghori, Gulapur, Hanokhar, Harbari Lakhapur, Isawta, Itava Kala, Jamua, Jarar, Jathara, Jora, Jore, Kakrahi, Kalyanpur, Kanchanpur, Kardaha, Kharka Khas, Khatauni, Khaur, Kona, Kunchi, Kurki Khurd, Lutar, Madaraha, Mai Kala, Majhila, Merara, Mudpela, Narir, Nevada, Pachauha, Pal Patti, Patai Dandi, Piparau, Pirhata Bisaura, Pura Lachchan, Renga, Shahpur Kala, Shahpur Khurd, Shamlipur, Siki Khurd, Singhpur Kala, Singhpur Khurd, Sohagi, Sukath, Sukulvan, Suraicha, Tenduva Khurd, Tigja, Udhrenga, Usaki	72	48%
4	32.8-37.4	Atkaiya Salaiya, Barsaita, Beri, Bhadevara, Bhasunder Kala, Bisari, Dari, Dasauti, Delaunha, Dharehatha, Gaderiya, Gaura, Ghosala, Gosauvara Khurd, Hargarh, Jhadiyahi, Kharka Dabar, Kotar, Lohara, Lotad, Mahuli Kala, Majhiyari, Mamoli, Maraha, Mejiya, Misrapur, Nevariya, Panti, Pura Chandel, Rauuni, Salaiya Khurd, Siki Khurd, Silaudhi Kala, Sirkhiri, Son Barsi, Suhas, Sujani Samodha, Tendua Kalan, Viswanathpur	39	26%
5	37.4-42	Bihyan khurd, Fachkari, Gadevara, Lakhanpur, Patehara, Pathara, Pausiya Jamaniya, Sirhir	8	5.33
Total			150	100

Source: Generated through data collected by the researcher during field visits in 2022.

In the following map, the darker shades represent the villages of lower order in the devised social index while lighter shades represent the better off villages based on the data collected. Villages with no colour represent the uninhabited villages.

Source: Analysed by the researcher through data collected during field visits in 2022. From the map, it can be concluded that regions in the southern and eastern part of the block, which are in darker shades are dissatisfied by the educational facilities in their area. While the villages falling in the central and the western parts of the block are lighter shades are in a relatively better situation with respect to educational centres and facilities. The highest score of 42 is in Lakhanpur village indicating the least desirable conditions in all the indicators used in this study. Gopalpur, Kauhat and Kurki Kalan on the other hand has the least score, indicating one of the best situations across all the parameters considered in this study. If we study in absolute numbers, the responses can be represented to show what are the issues and challenges that the people face in availing education facilities.

Table 3: Number and percentage of respondents in each category

S. No.	Category	Number of Respondents	% Respondents
1	No Issues	92	10.22
2	Poor performance of teachers in school	33	3.67
3	Lack of quality education	65	7.22
4	Distance to school	82	9.11
5	Lack of schools in the area	84	9.33
6	Lack of transportation	185	20.56
7	High school fees	359	39.89
Total		900	100

Source: Analysed by the researcher through data collected during field visits in 2022. The remarkably high count of **high school fees** highlights economic disparities as a significant cause hindering education to children in the study area- making education primarily accessible to economically advantaged families. These difficulties are intensified by factors such as gender and caste. (Subrahmanian, R., 1999). Lack of transportation is the second most common challenge according to the collected data. Insufficient road infrastructure and limited public transportation options prevent students from reaching schools. The issue of **Distance to School** is another major roadblock. The geographical challenges posed by schools situated in the remote locations or irregular of these villages make it physically difficult for students to access schools. Moreover, safety concerns often deter parents from sending their children to school when the journey is long and distant. One of the primary challenges is the availability of educational infrastructure. Infrastructure plays a vital role in supporting high-quality elementary education. As per the Right to Education Act (RTE) 2009, each school is mandated to have essential facilities, including classrooms, teachers, separate toilets for boys and girls, safe drinking water, a playground, a kitchen for mid-day meals, a boundary wall, electricity, and computer facilities. (Majhi and Mallick, 2019). Heyneman's (1980) research, conducted in both developed and developing nations, has led him to the conclusion that students in developing countries exhibit significantly lower performance levels compared to their counterparts in developed countries. This disparity is attributed to insufficient and substandard school facilities in the developing nations. **Lack of Quality Education** is a prominent concern, primarily driven by the inadequate allocation of resources. Ineffectively designed and poorly maintained buildings have a detrimental impact on student learning, with those from low-income families being more prone to attending schools housed in such inadequate buildings. (Filardo, Vincent, & Sullivan, 2019). The paramount concern within the Indian public education system is its substandard quality. Even in states that are considered educationally advanced, an unacceptably small percentage of children who successfully complete all primary school

grades demonstrate functional literacy. (Bajpai and Goyal, 2004) Moreover, the absence of modern technology and infrastructure, limits students' access to a broader range of knowledge. Research conducted in both developed and developing countries has consistently demonstrated that these elements play a significant role in influencing students' academic achievement. (Mwamwenda & Mwamwenda, 1987). The **Poor Performance of Teachers in Schools** compounds these issues. Today the modern small schools in rural India are found struggling, with limited human and physical resources, low enrolment and high incidence of teacher and student absenteeism. (Diwan, R. ,2015). Low pay, limited recognition, and challenging working conditions lead to demotivated educators who struggle to provide the level of instruction necessary for students' success and development. Taking into consideration this widely accepted fact, there has been a significant emphasis on education in India since the country gained independence. However, ensuring quality education in rural India has posed a major challenge for the government. India has perceived education as a primary means of fostering social change. (Kapur, Radhika, 2018)

The educational infrastructure in Meja block contains of schools ranging from Pre-Primary to senior secondary, and colleges of various streams like- Degree colleges, Management colleges, Engineering and Medical colleges, Vocational training institute etc. a list of all these educational facilities of various streams is given below:

Table 4: Spatial distribution of educational centres located in villages of Meja block.

S. No.	Category	Names of the villages it is situated
1	Pre-Primary school	Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Dasauti ,Dighalo ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Gunai Gaharpur ,Kalyanpur ,Kona ,Kotar ,Kulbhasa ,Lohara ,Meja Khas ,Nartir ,Nevariya ,Pathara ,Son Barsi ,Usaki
2	Primary school	Atari Amiliya ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhabhaur ,Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Bhatauti ,Bhoj Purva ,Bisari ,Busaka ,Chandhash ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Dari ,Derhan ,Dighalo ,Gadevara ,Gadurahi ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Gulalpur ,Gunai Gaharpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jamua ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khaur ,Kohrar ,Kona ,Kotar ,Kulbhasa ,Lohara ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Maraha ,Meja Khas ,Mejiya ,Merara ,Mojara ,Nartir ,Nevada ,Nevariya ,Panti ,Pathara ,Pura Lachchan ,Shahpur Kala ,Shamlipur ,Sirkhiri ,Suhas ,Sujani Samodha ,Suraicha ,Tigja ,Usaki
3	Middle school	Belahan ,Beri ,Bhaiya ,Bhatauti ,Bhoj Purva ,Busaka ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Derhan ,Gadurahi ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghori ,Gulalpur ,Gunai Gaharpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jamua ,Kharka Dabar ,Kohrar ,Kulbhasa ,Lohara ,Mai Kala ,Meja Khas ,Mojara ,Nartir ,Nevariya ,Panti ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Pura Lachchan ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shamlipur ,Suhas ,Suraicha ,Usaki
4	Secondary school	Bhatauti ,Bhoj Purva ,Busaka ,Dighalo ,Gulalpur ,Gunai Gaharpur ,Kohrar ,Mai Kala ,Meja Khas ,Nartir ,Nevariya ,Panti ,Pura Lachchan ,Usaki
5	Senior Secondary school	Bhatauti ,Busaka ,Gulalpur ,Kohrar ,Meja Khas ,Nartir ,Nevariya ,Panti
6	Degree college of arts science & commerce	Busaka ,Chandra Udaya ,Gopalpur ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Gulalpur ,Jore ,Khatauni ,Kotar ,Lohara ,Majhiyari ,Nartir

7	Engineering college	Chandra Udaya ,Gopalpur ,Jore ,Khatauni ,Kotar ,Lohara ,Majhiyari ,Nartir
8	Medical College	Majhiyari ,Nartir
9	Management Institute	Kotar ,Lohara ,Mojara ,Shahpur Kala
10	Polytechnic	Nartir
11	Vocational Training Institute	Dharehatha

Source: Analysed from District Census Handbook, Prayagraj, Part A, 2011.

However, there are many villages which do not have facilities of their own. The nearest educational facility of various levels is situated at a distance. The following tables gives a list of the villages where a particular educational facility is available at a distance range- villages with facilities in the range of less than 5 km, within the range of 5-10 km and at a distance of beyond 10 kms.

Table 5: Spatial distribution of educational centres located within 5 kilometres in villages of Meja block.

S. No.	Category	Names of the villages it is situated
1	Pre-Primary school	Amkachha ,Belahan ,Beri ,Busaka ,Chandra Udaya ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gaharpur Khurd ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Gulalpur ,Isawta ,Jathara ,Kanchanpur ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khatauni ,Kurki Khurd ,Marar ,Mejiya ,Mojara ,Narir ,Nevada ,Panti ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Khurd ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Sujani Samodha ,Tigja ,Udhrenga ,Viswanathpur
2	Primary school	Amkachha ,Bairghat ,Chandra Udaya ,Dasauti ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gaharpur Khurd ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Jore ,Karah ,Khatauni ,Kurki Khurd ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Marar ,Misrapur ,Narir ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Siki Khurd ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sukath ,Udhrenga ,Viswanathpur
3	Middle school	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Bhabhaur ,Bhadevara ,Chandhash ,Chandra Udaya ,Chapro ,Dari ,Dasauti ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Ghoraha ,Ghosala ,Gopalpur ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kardaha ,Khatauni ,Kona ,Kotar ,Kurki Khurd ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Marar ,Mejiya ,Merara ,Misrapur ,Narir ,Nevada ,Siki Khurd ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sujani Samodha ,Sukath ,Tigja ,Udhrenga ,Viswanathpur
4	Secondary school	Amkachha ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhadevara ,Bisari ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Dasauti ,Gadevara ,Gadurahi ,Ghoraha ,Ghosala ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Isawta ,Jamua ,Kanchanpur ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Kona ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Kurki Khurd ,Mai Khurd ,Marar ,Mejiya ,Misrapur ,Mojara ,Pura Chandel ,Shahpur Kala ,Shahpur Khurd ,Sirkhiri ,Son Barsi ,Sujani Samodha ,Sukath ,Tigja ,Udhrenga ,Viswanathpur
5	Senior Secondary school	Belahan ,Beri ,Bhadevara ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Dasauti ,Gadevara ,Gadurahi ,Ghoraha ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Isawta ,Jamua ,Kanchanpur ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Marar ,Mejiya ,Mojara ,Pura Chandel ,Pura Lachchan ,Sirkhiri ,Son Barsi ,Tigja ,Udhrenga ,Viswanathpur

6	Degree college of arts science & commerce	Bhadevara ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Dasauti ,Gadurahi ,Ghoraha ,Jamua ,Kardaha ,Kulbhasa ,Marar ,Mojara ,Sirkhiri ,Son Barsi ,Tigja ,Udhrenga
7	Engineering college	Mojara ,Tigja
8	Medical College	Pura Lachchan ,Viswanathpur
9	Management Institute	NIL
10	Polytechnic	Kardaha ,Pura Lachchan ,Sirkhiri ,Tigja
11	Vocational Training Institute	Gadurahi ,Jamua ,Karah ,Sujani Samodha

Source: Analysed from District Census Handbook, Prayagraj, Part A, 2011.

Table 6: Spatial distribution of educational centres located within 5- 10 kilometres in villages of Meja block.

S. No.	Category	Names of the villages it is situated
1	Pre-Primary school	Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Bhabhaur ,Bisari ,Derhan ,Dharehatha ,Gat ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Gopalpur ,Itava Kala ,Jore ,Karah ,Khaur ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Shahpur Kala
2	Primary school	Ghosala
3	Middle school	Bisari ,Jore ,Kharka Khas ,Khaur
4	Secondary school	Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Bhabhaur ,Chapro ,Dari ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Fachkari ,Gat ,Gaura ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Khaur ,Mahuli Kala ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Narir ,Nevada ,Pathara ,Rauuni ,Shamlipur ,Sohagi ,Suhas ,Suraicha
5	Senior Secondary school	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bhabhaur ,Bisari ,Dari ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Khaur ,Kona ,Kurki Khurd ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Merara ,Misrapur ,Narir ,Nevada ,Pathara ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shamlipur ,Siki Khurd ,Sohagi ,Suhas ,Sujani Samodha ,Sukath ,Suraicha ,Usaki
6	Degree college of arts science & commerce	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bhabhaur ,Bisari ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Fachkari ,Itava Kala ,Kalyanpur ,Kharka Dabar ,Khaur ,Kurki Kalan ,Kurki Khurd ,Mahuli Kala ,Majhila ,Merara ,Misrapur ,Narir ,Nevada ,Panti ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Shamlipur ,Sohagi ,Suhas ,Sujani Samodha ,Usaki ,Viswanathpur
7	Engineering college	Bhabhaur ,Bisari ,Panti ,Shahpur Khurd ,Usaki
8	Medical College	Amkachha ,Dari ,Kurki Khurd ,Misrapur
9	Management Institute	Kona ,Merara ,Nevariya
10	Polytechnic	Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Busaka ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Dari ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Khaur ,Kona ,Viswanathpur
11	Vocational Training Institute	Kulbhasa ,Panti ,Son Barsi ,Sukath

Source: Analysed from District Census Handbook, Prayagraj, Part A, 2011.

Table 7: Spatial distribution of educational centres located beyond 10 kilometres in villages of Meja block.

S. No.	Category	Names of the villages it is situated
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1	Pre-Primary school	Bhoj Purva ,Chandhash
2	Primary school	NIL
3	Middle school	Gaharpur Khurd
4	Secondary school	Bhaiya ,Chandhash ,Chandra Udaya ,Gaharpur Khurd ,Gopalpur ,Jore ,Karah ,Khatauni ,Kotar ,Lohara
5	Senior Secondary school	Bairghat, Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Chandhash ,Chandra Udaya ,Chapro ,Gopalpur ,Jore ,Karah ,Kharka Khas ,Khatauni ,Kotar ,Lohara
6	Degree college of arts science & commerce	Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Chandhash ,Chapro ,Derhan ,Etawa Khurd ,Gadevara ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Isawta ,Jathara ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kharka Khas ,Kona ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Nevariya ,Shahpur Kala ,Suraicha
7	Engineering college	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Busaka ,Chandhash ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Derhan ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gadurahi ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Gulalpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khaur ,Kona ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Kurki Khurd ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Marar ,Misrapur ,Nevada ,Nevariya ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shamlipur ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sahas ,Sujani Samodha ,Suraicha ,Viswanathpur
8	Medical College	Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhabhaur ,Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Bisari ,Busaka ,Chandhash ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Derhan ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gadurahi ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Gulalpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khaur ,Kona ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Marar ,Nevada ,Nevariya ,Panti ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shamlipur ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sahas ,Sujani Samodha ,Suraicha ,Tigja ,Usaki
9	Management Institute	Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhabhaur ,Bhadevara ,Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Bisari ,Busaka ,Chandhash ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Derhan ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Gulalpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khaur ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Marar ,Misrapur ,Nevada ,Panti ,Pathara ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Khurd ,Shamlipur ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sahas ,Sujani Samodha ,Suraicha ,Tigja ,Usaki ,Viswanathpur
10	Polytechnic	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhabhaur ,Bhoj Purva ,Bisari ,Chandhash ,Chandra Udaya ,Derhan ,Dharehatha ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Ghosala ,Gopalpur ,Gulalpur ,Isawta ,Itava Kala ,Jathara ,Jore ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Karah ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khatauni ,Kotar ,Kulbhasa ,Kurki Kalan ,Kurki Khurd ,Lohara ,Mahuli Kala ,Mai Kala ,Mai Khurd ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Marar ,Merara ,Misrapur ,Mojara ,Nevada ,Panti ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shahpur Khurd ,Shamlipur ,Sohagi ,Son Barsi ,Sahas ,Sujani Samodha ,Suraicha ,Usaki

11	Vocational Training Institute	Amkachha ,Atari Amiliya ,Bairghat ,Belahan ,Beri ,Bhabhaur ,Bhaiya ,Bhoj Purva ,Bisari ,Chandhash ,Chandra Udaya ,Chapartala Tappa Chaurasi ,Chapro ,Dari ,Derhan ,Dhauhan Chehra ,Dighalo ,Etawa Khurd ,Fachkari ,Gadevara ,Gat ,Gaura ,Ghoraha ,Ghori ,Gopalpur ,Gosauvara Khurd ,Isawta ,Jathara ,Jore ,Kalyanpur ,Kanchanpur ,Kardaha ,Kharka Dabar ,Kharka Khas ,Khatauni ,Khaur ,Kona ,Kotar ,Kurki Kalan ,Kurki Khurd ,Lohara ,Mai Kala ,Majhila ,Majhiyari ,Misrapur ,Mojara ,Nevada ,Pathara ,Pura Chandel ,Pura Lachchan ,Rauuni ,Shahpur Kala ,Shahpur Khurd ,Shamlipur ,Sirkhiri ,Sohagi ,Suhas ,Suraicha ,Tigja ,Usaki ,Viswanathpur
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Source: Analysed from District Census Handbook, Prayagraj, Part A, 2011.

Review of Government schemes related to education:

Governments at the state and national levels have launched several schemes to foster education. Both central and state governments have been continuously assigning high priority to expanding the provision of education and enhancing participation, particularly at the primary level. (Hilland Chalaux, 2011) For over two decades, there has been a notable and growing commitment from the Indian government to enhance access to its educational system, particularly in elementary education. This commitment is evident through a continual increase in resource mobilization and the implementation of significant and innovative initiatives, such as the Mid-Day Meal Scheme (B, Florian, 2008). While launching these schemes the state which assumes the role of a welfare state keeps in mind the fact that accessibility to education especially for weaker sections of the society as well as for girls is still difficult to access. The first MDG goal aims for all children to complete primary school by 2015, while the second goal targets achieving gender equality at all levels of education by the same year. (Glewwe, P, Kremer, M). Below is a list of several government schemes launched by national government along with launch year and the main objective of the scheme.

Table 8: List of National Government Schemes

S. No.	Scheme Name	Launch Year	Main Objectives
1	Mid-Day Meal Scheme	1995	Improve nutrition levels among school children, encourage regular attendance, and reduce drop-out rates by providing a daily nutritious meal during school hours.
2	National Scheme of Incentive to Girls	2008	Promote the enrolment and retention of girl students in schools by providing financial incentives and removing socio-economic barriers to their education.
3	Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA)	2001	Attain universalization of elementary education by guaranteeing access, enrollment, and retention of all children aged 6-14 years, with focus on quality improvement.
4	Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA)	2009	Enhance access to secondary education and improve its quality by providing financial assistance for infrastructure development, teacher training, and curriculum renewal.
5	National Means-Cum-Merit Scholarship Scheme	2008	Avail financial assistance to meritorious students from low-income households to reduce the dropout rate at the class eight and encourage them to pursue higher secondary education.
6	Pradhan Mantri Vidya Lakshmi Karyakram	2015	Streamline the process of education loans and scholarships by establishing a single window platform where students can easily access information about different loan schemes and scholarships.
7	Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao	2015	Encourage the education of the girl child, address the challenge of declining child sex ratio, and prevent female infanticide through awareness campaigns and financial support.
8	National Scholarship Portal	2015	Create a transparent and efficient platform for students to apply for and avail the several scholarships given by the central and state governments, and other agencies.
9	Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan	2018	Ensure holistic development of school education by integrating various schemes, improving infrastructure, enhancing teacher quality, and promoting inclusive education.
10	Digital India for School	2014	Promote digital literacy in schools by providing infrastructure, teacher training, and digital content, with the goal of

			integrating technology into the education system.
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Source: Data collected and consolidated in a table by the researcher from government websites.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the status of education in Meja reflects a struggle marked by several common issues prevalent in rural areas across the country. Recurring challenges are: inadequacy of educational infrastructure and insufficient teaching resources, dearth of trained and qualified educators and socio-economic constraints. In the context of government schemes, while commendable initiatives have been implemented to address these challenges, their effectiveness remains dependent on efficient execution and sustained community engagement. Adequate monitoring mechanisms are essential to ensure that the intended benefits of these schemes reach the grassroots level, fostering an environment conducive to education.

To elevate the status of education in Meja block and similar rural settings, there is a pressing need for comprehensive strategies that go beyond infrastructure development. Interventions must encompass teacher training programs, community awareness initiatives, and efforts to mitigate socio-economic barriers. Additionally, leveraging technology for remote learning and creating tailored solutions that resonate with the local context can play a pivotal role in enhancing educational outcomes. Effective planning of education facilities must be a team effort. (Schwehr, 1962). Sustainable progress requires a holistic approach, combining effective policy implementation, community involvement, and innovative solutions to foster a transformative impact on the educational status of the region.

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